

Conductance Study of Mixed Halocobaltates(II) in Acetonitrile

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The values of molar conductance of some mixed** tri-, mixed tetra- and mixed pentahalocobaltates(II) at single concentration have been found out which indicate that these compounds behave as 1 : 1, 2 : 1 and 3 : 1 electrolytes respectively in solution; for mixed tetra- and mixed pentahalocobaltates(II) these conclusions are in contrast to those from electronic and far i.r. spectral behaviour. An explanation for this anomaly has been advanced. For the mixed trihalocobaltates(II) equivalent conductance has been found out at different concentrations and Debye-Hückel-Onsager equation has been applied to confirm the 1 : 1 electrolyte nature. The calculated and experimental slopes of the plots of $\Lambda_0 - \Lambda_e$ vs \sqrt{c} have been compared.

WE have recently isolated and characterized a few mixed** halocobaltates (II)¹⁻⁵. Apart from electronic spectral, far i.r. and magnetic studies which we have already reported, we have now carried out conductance measurements of these complexes in acetonitrile which are being reported in the present article. Use of conductance measurements in the study of coordination complexes has been, for long, in vogue for the characterization of the electrolyte type, and therefore, to some extent, the structure of the complex in solution. Most of the conductance data reported in literature to characterize a given coordination compound are at a fixed concentration ($\sim 10^{-3}M$) but recently this method has been criticized⁶, and measurement of conductance over a range of concentration has been suggested to arrive at unambiguous results. In the present work measurements were made at fixed concentration for all the three types of mixed halocobaltates (II), namely mixed tri-, tetra- and pentahalocobaltates (II) but measurements over a range of concentration were made only for mixed trihalocobaltates (II). The reason for this choice is discussed later.

Experimental

The methods of preparation of the complexes have already been reported^{1,2,5}. All measurements were carried out on a WG Pye conductance unit. A conductance cell with lightly platinized electrode was used. It was standardized by a standard solution of A. R. potassium chloride. BDH acetonitrile was purified by the method of Walden and Birr⁷; the specific conductance of the purified solvent was found to be 2×10^{-7} mhos cm^{-1} (reported value 5.9×10^{-8} mhos cm^{-1})⁶. Conductance of all the complexes were measured at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$ at $1 \times 10^{-3}M$ and $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ concentrations. For trihalocobaltates

(II) the measurements were carried out at different concentrations in the range 10^{-2} to 10^{-4} eq/l at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Treatment of Data :

Molar conductance :

Λ_M at single concentration was calculated by using the equation $\Lambda_M = \frac{1000k}{c}$... (1)

where k is specific conductance and c is molarity of the solution.

Debye-Hückel-Onsager equation⁸ :

The equation $\Lambda_e = \Lambda_0 - (A + B\Lambda_0\omega) \sqrt{c}$... (2) was used for analysing the data obtained at different concentrations where the symbols have their usual significance.

First Λ_e values were plotted against \sqrt{c} and the linear portion of the plot was extrapolated to zero concentration to obtain Λ_0 value. Equation (2) on rearrangement gives

$$\Lambda_0 - \Lambda_e = (A + B\Lambda_0\omega) \sqrt{c} \quad \dots (3)$$

The slope of the line obtained by plotting $(\Lambda_0 - \Lambda_e)$ against \sqrt{c} gave the experimental value of the factor $(A + B\Lambda_0\omega)$ which was compared with the theoretically calculated value of this factor to give an idea about the type of electrolyte under study. This factor was calculated from the expressions for A, B and ω ⁸. In calculating ω for a 1 : 1 electrolyte λ_0^+ and λ_0^- , the limiting ionic mobilities of the cation

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**The term "mixed" is applied to halocobaltates(II) having more than one kind of halogens e.g., $CoCl_2Br_{2-2}$ and "simple" to those having only one kind of halogen e.g., $CoCl_2^{-4}$.

and anion respectively need not be known as they cancel out in the calculation. in fact double salts containing tetrahedral Co(II)⁶ like the earlier reported Cs₃CoCl₅ being Cs₂CoCl₄.

TABLE 2—PARAMETERS FOR DEBYE-HÜCKEL-ONSAGER EQUATION

Compound	Temperature : 25±0.5°C, η=0.345 centipoise, D=36.7, E=(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ N ⁺					Slope (cal.)	Slope (exp.)
	Λ ₀	A	B	ω	Slope (exp.)		
E(CoCl ₂ I)	159	228	1.224	0.586	417	342	1.22
E(CoBr ₂ I)	162.5	228	1.224	0.586	571	345	1.66

Results and Discussion

The results for single concentration measurements are given in Table 1. The parameters for Debye-Hückel-Onsager equation and the experimental and calculated slopes are reported in Table 2 for mixed trihalocobaltates.

TABLE 1—Λ_M VALUES AT (25±0.5)°C, SOLVENT : ACETONITRILE*

B = (n-C₄H₉)₄N⁺; E=(C₂H₅)₄N⁺

Compound	Λ _M (mhos cm ² mol ⁻¹) (Conc. 1.00 × 10 ⁻³ M)	Λ _M (mhos cm ² mol ⁻¹) (Conc. 2.00 × 10 ⁻³ M)
E(CoCl ₂ I)	145	140
E(CoBr ₂ I)	144	137
E ₂ (CoCl ₄)	316	290
E ₂ (CoCl ₂ Br ₂)	307	284
E ₂ (CoCl ₂ I ₂)	316	298
E ₂ (CoBr ₂ I ₂)	350	322
E ₃ (CoCl ₅)	414	390
E ₃ (CoCl ₃ Br ₂)	357	315
E ₃ (CoCl ₃ Br ₃)	355	315
E ₃ (CoClBr ₄)	364	327
B ₃ (CoCl ₂ I ₃)	343	303
B ₃ (CoBr ₂ I ₃)	350	315

*Range for various electrolyte-types in this solvent are⁶

Electrolyte	Range for Λ _M
1 : 1	120-160
1 : 2	240-320
1 : 3	340-420

Single concentration molar conductance values :

From an examination of the molar conductance values at single concentration (Table 1). it is evident that they fall within the generally acceptable range of the different kinds of electrolytes in acetonitrile, thus apparently confirming the presence of ionic species manifest in the molecular formula of the respective complex. For example, Λ_M for [(C₂H₅)₄N]₂ [CoCl₂Br₂] is 284 (mhos cm² mol⁻¹) which is well within the range 240-320 accepted for a (1 : 2) electrolyte in acetonitrile. The values for pentahalocobaltates (II) fall in the range of (1 : 3) electrolytes thus leading one to conclude that triply charged Co(II) would exist in solution.

These results are surprising in view of our conclusion from far i.r. and electronic spectral results that the pentahalocobaltates (II) are

CsCl⁹. Further it has been concluded from the solution spectral results of mixed tetra- and pentahalocobaltates (II) that the solvent replaces one of the halides from the coordination sphere and thus the original species is destroyed, resulting in solution containing a mixture of species¹⁰. Similar observation has been reported for simple tetrahalocobaltates (II) earlier¹¹⁻¹³, viz. CoCl₄²⁻ exists mainly as (CoCl₃X)⁻ and Cl⁻ in an organic solvent. In case of mixed trihalocobaltates (II) entrance of the solvent molecule into coordination sphere does not disturb the original halides attached to Co (II) except that the bridge is broken and the fourth coordination site is occupied by a solvent molecule [A one dimensional chain type structure with bridging halogen and tetrahedrally coordinated Co (II) has been proposed for the mixed trihalocobaltates (II)⁹. Thus the value of Λ_M falling in the expected range for a particular electrolyte in case of tetra- and pentahalocobaltates (II) gives only a deceptive result about the number of ions present in the solution.

The deceptive result for the tetra- and pentahalocobaltates (II) may be explained if the following points are taken into consideration : (i) Tetrahalo- and pentahalocobaltates (II) dissociate in acetonitrile to give rise to mixture comprising, mainly univalent negatively charged species e.g., CoCl₄²⁻ gives rise to (CoCl₃CH₃CN)⁻ and Cl⁻ (a small amount of CoCl₄²⁻ may also be present) and (CoCl₄Br)³⁻ which has been shown to (CoCl₃Br)²⁻. Cl⁻⁵ will give rise to (CoCl₃CH₃CN)⁻, Br⁻ and Cl⁻; [a small amount of (CoCl₃Br)²⁻ may also be present]; it may be noted that in (CoCl₃Br)²⁻ bromide will be replaced from the coordination sphere by CH₃CN molecule since it is more susceptible to solvent attack than chloride¹¹.

(ii) It is known that it is not possible¹⁴ to distinguish, by conductance measurements, between a solution containing a mixture of species and the one containing single species, if the mobilities of the ions present in the mixture and that of the single species are almost the same. Thus, taking CoCl₄²⁻ as an example, which gives a mixture of COCl₄²⁻ (very small amount), (CoCl₃CH₃CN)⁻ and Cl⁻ in solution¹¹, the mobilities of the latter two ions may not be very much different from each other and this may be explained in terms of (a) the electrical field around the ion and (b) the size of the ion. A smaller ion e.g., Cl⁻, is expected to move faster than

$(\text{CoCl}_2\text{CH}_3\text{CN})^-$ but it would gather more electrical field as compared to the bigger ion and thus its movement would be hampered by the ionic atmosphere of opposite charges around it. Thus a situation exists where the mobilities of the ions present in solution may not be very much different from each other. For example, a comparison of λ_0^- values of Cl^- and BCl_4^- shows that these are nearly the same (91.6 and 95.2 respectively)¹⁵ even though the ions differ considerably in their size.

Based on the above arguments the observation that the Λ_M values for tetrahalocobaltates (II) fall in the range of (1 : 2) electrolyte inspite of its dissociation into monovalent species may be explained in the following way. In the equation (I) used for the calculation of Λ_M , concentration term is in the denominator and while calculating Λ_M for CoCl_4^{2-} without taking into consideration its dissociation, the concentration used is just nearly the half of the total concentration of all the species present in the solution and that is why the expected value for a (1 : 1) electrolyte gets nearly doubled to fall in the range of a (1 : 2) electrolyte. Similarly for pentahalocobaltates (II) taking $(\text{CoCl}_3\text{CH}_3\text{CN})^-$, Br^- , Cl^- and $(\text{CoCl}_3\text{Br})^{2-}$ (very small amount) in solution the concentration (of monovalent species) is actually nearly thrice of what would be expected if $(\text{CoCl}_4\text{Br})^{3-}$ were present as such and hence the value falls in the range of (1 : 3) electrolyte.

In the light of above observations it is noteworthy that some of the earlier workers¹⁶⁻¹⁹ have measured the molar conductance of halometallates(II), MX_4^{2-} ($\text{M} = \text{Co}, \text{Ni}$; $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ or I) at fixed concentration in acetonitrile, nitromethane etc. and have characterized the complexes as various electrolyte types according to the accepted ranges. But in view of the solvent attack discussed above, these values do not represent the actual Λ_M values of the original tetrahedral species but instead, they represent like in the present work, Λ_M 's for a mixture of species.

Conductance over a range of Concentration :

The study was limited to trihalocobaltates (II) only since, as mentioned earlier the tetra- and pentahalocobaltates (II) give rise to a mixture of species and though the magnitude of Λ_M value for the trihalocobaltates (II) was sufficient enough to characterize them as (1 : 1) electrolytes in acetonitrile solution (Table 1) the view⁶ that the single concentration is frequently chosen arbitrarily and in many cases even for a series of related compounds is chosen differently, thus making the direct comparison difficult and that the method requires the assumption of a molecular weight which may well be erroneous, underscored the necessity of undertaking a study of conductance over a concentration range.

It had been mentioned earlier that trihalocobaltates (II) were shown to have a halo-bridged tetrahedral structure and a one dimensional chain structure was favoured vis-a-vis a dimeric unit structure². Now, in Table 1 the value of Λ_M , to take $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}][\text{CoCl}_2\text{I}]$ as an example, does fall in the accepted range for a (1 : 1) electrolyte, but the concentration used in calculating the Λ_M has the basis that $(\text{CoCl}_2\text{ICH}_3\text{CN})^-$ is present in solution and had it been supposed that the dimer species $(\text{Co}_2\text{Cl}_4\text{I}_2)^{2-}$ is present in solution, the concentration term would have become half of that used in $(\text{CoCl}_2\text{ICH}_3\text{CN})^-$ case bringing the Λ_M value within the range for a (1 : 2) electrolyte.

But in view of the chances that acetonitrile may break up the bridging bonds producing two $(\text{CoCl}_2\text{ICH}_3\text{CN})^-$ species from one $(\text{CoCl}_4\text{I}_2)^{2-}$ species, the dimer if present in solid state, will not be present in solution and the solution will behave just as if a monomer is present in solid state and has become solvent-coordinated on putting in solvent. However, Bobbit and Gladden²⁰ have, by molecular weight determination of $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}][\text{CoCl}_3]$ in acetonitrile at various concentration, shown that in solution $(\text{Co}_2\text{Cl}_6)^{2-}$ species is present. And if their results are to be believed and it is supposed that the dimer, if present in solid state, is retained in solution without any solvent attack, in case of the complexes under study, the Λ_M measurement at a fixed concentration, as shown in the previous paragraph cannot distinguish between a monomer and a dimer. So, to resolve this ambiguity measurement of conductance over a range of concentration was carried out.

A comparison of the experimental and calculated values of the slope (Table 2) shows that though the former are greater than the latter (an explanation for this discrepancy is given later) the complexes at least in solution, can safely be taken to be (1 : 1) electrolyte as the theoretical value of slope for a (1 : 2) electrolyte under the same conditions and with Λ_0 as reported in Table 2 will be ~ 700 which is far above either of the two experimental values of slopes for the complexes under study. It may be noted that lower slope value than the theoretical one should not be observed for a given type of electrolyte even when completely dissociated. And even if solvent coordination by replacement of one of the halides in the coordination sphere of the possible dimer species in solution is allowed, the value of the theoretical slope may still be higher if the same equivalent weight as calculated for the dimer species is used for calculating Λ_0 . Thus in the case of the mixed trihalocobaltates (II) dimeric species is not present in solution and they are (1 : 1) electrolytes.

The range of concentration used in this study was $10^{-3} - 10^{-4}$ eq/l which is the range widely used by other workers²¹⁻²⁴. Noticable association is observed at a higher concentration²⁴. The lower

concentration range was also limited due to the experimental errors in measuring conductance²⁵. An interesting feature in the plots of Δc vs \sqrt{c} is that beyond $\sim 10^{-4}$ eq/l linearity is lost and an upward trend in the curve is noticed. This observation may be explained by solvolysis reaction of the type

where $n=0, 1, 2$ and $m=n+1$.¹ Thus an increase in the number of ions causes an unusual rise in conductance. Similar phenomenon has been reported by Cotton *et al*²¹.

Table 2 shows that for both the mixed trihalocobaltates (II) the experimental value of the slope is greater than the theoretically calculated one for a (1 : 1) electrolyte. Such a variation is not an unusual phenomenon, particularly in non aqueous solvents and is attributable to association or incomplete dissociation of the electrolyte present in solution. When the dissociation is incomplete, the observed conductance is less than what should have been observed at that particular concentration with the result that the ratio

$\frac{\Delta_0 - \Delta_c}{\sqrt{c}} = (A + B\Delta_{0\omega})$ increases beyond the expected value. The ratio of the experimental slope to the calculated slope is more in case of $(\text{CoBr}_2\text{I})^-$ than in case of $(\text{CoCl}_2\text{I})^-$ which indicates that the degree of dissociation is more for the latter. A range of similar ratios (1.038–1.699) has been reported by Daggett and Harkness²³ for tetraalkylammonium halides in acetonitrile.

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